

TECHNOLOGY OF APPLICATION OF GEOSYNTHETIC MATERIAL IN PRODUCTION AND CONSTRUCTION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7728460>

Annotation. This article provides an opportunity to consider the use of geosynthetic materials (hereinafter referred to as GM) in accordance with design solutions in the construction, reconstruction and overhaul of roads, city streets, driveways, high-load areas, parking lots and other structures.

Key words and phrases: Basalt, geogrid, SBNP, geosynthetic material, basalt fibers.

Basalt is an igneous rock formed by the rapid cooling of lava that erupted onto the surface of the earth. Basalt is heavier than granite, but also stronger than it. Basalt melts at 1100–1200°C. There are variations of the rock, the melting point of which reaches 1450 degrees. Do not take a stone and strong chemicals. Basalt is resistant to all acids and alkalis.

From this material "MEGA INVEST INDUSTRIAL" the organization produces products for the construction industry. Basalt building mesh and reinforcement, which come to replace obsolete metal.

Pic. 1- Basalt grid mining

Applications in construction

- for reinforcing horizontal seams of masonry walls made of various materials in order to increase its bearing capacity under various types of its stress state (compression, tension in bending along a tied section, when shearing along a tied section) and solidity.
- for reinforcing the masonry of walls made of large-format ceramic stone with a voidage of more than 30% to prevent mortar from entering the joints of the masonry and to ensure the level of thermal conductivity of stone walls.
- as bonding elements in two-layer walls, with brick lining with the main inner layer of various wall materials (silicate and ceramic bricks, large-format stones, cellular concrete.
- for reinforcing the plaster layer of walls made of various stone materials in order to increase their solidity, seismic resistance and crack resistance.

- to reinforce brick walls and pillars by installing composite mesh bandages.
- to strengthen load-bearing, self-supporting and non-bearing (partitions) walls made of various stone materials.
- for reinforcing floor screeds from mortar and concrete mixtures in order to increase their strength and prevent the formation of shrinkage cracks.

➤
Pic.

2-

Applications of GM in construction

The main purpose of the use of HM is to ensure the reliable functioning of the road or its individual elements in difficult conditions of construction and operation. The installation of additional layers of GM allows you to increase the operational reliability and service life of the structure or its individual elements, the quality of work, simplify the construction technology, reduce construction time, reduce the consumption of traditional building materials, the volume of earthworks, and the material consumption of the structure.

Geogrid: A flat geosynthetic material having regular, stable shape through cells larger than the largest cross-sectional dimension of the ribs, formed by extruding, gluing, thermally bonding, or interlacing the ribs, resisting tension (external loads) and acting as structural reinforcement.

Domestic and foreign experience in the use of geosynthetic materials shows their versatility (extensive field of application), cost-effectiveness (reducing construction and operation costs, saving building materials, reducing the time of work, increasing the time between repairs), and environmental friendliness. All decisions related to the use of geosynthetic materials must be based on design solutions developed taking into account the relevant documents.

Geogrids made of basalt fiber grade SBNP produced according to specifications are recommended to be used as reinforcing layers in the construction of roads, airfields, sites for various purposes and in other geotechnical structures.

In cases of construction on weak foundations, in the presence of waterlogged cohesive soils, water-saturated sandy soils, it is recommended to use as a reinforcing element geogrids made of basalt fiber grade SBNP produced according to TU 24373711-001:2018 in combination with a separating layer of non-woven geosynthetic material.

When constructing geosynthetic layers from a geogrid, the following operations are additionally introduced into the applied technological maps:

- preparation of the base for laying the geogrid;
- transportation, distribution of geogrid rolls over the site, their laying;
- backfilling of the overlying layer onto the geogrid, its distribution and compaction.

Substrate preparation consists of profiling its surface and compacting it. Shrubs, trees are cut down and cut down at the same level with the surface. In this case, uprooting of stumps may not be performed. In the presence of stumps, bumps, depressions, a leveling layer should be poured on the surface of the base of the embankment before laying the geogrid to eliminate irregularities. The size of the irregularities should not exceed 5 cm. If at the time of work on the site there are surface waters, then a leveling sand layer is poured. When laying layers of geogrids at the base of an embankment, arranged on soft soils, preparation may not be performed if there is no danger of damage to the geogrid [1, 2].

Pic. 3- Preparation of earthworks using geogrids

Geogrid rolls are transported to the place of work immediately before laying and distributed along the length of the work site through a distance corresponding to the length of the web in the roll. If access to the construction site is difficult, special measures should be taken to organize temporary access roads for the period of construction. In a convenient place, close to the object of work, a working platform and a storage platform should be arranged, on which the geogrid is stored and prepared (if necessary) for laying [1, 2].

Before filling the soil, the quality of the laid material is checked by visual inspection and fixing the continuity, the size of the overlap, the quality of the joining of the canvases. Based on the results of the inspection, an act is drawn up for hidden work, which contains the results of the inspection, data on the supplier and the characteristics of the used geogrid, indicated in the passport for the batch or on the labels of the rolls, as well as data obtained when the geogrid was accepted by the contractor's laboratory [4, 5].

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